

Online repository

PerSpecML: A Perspective-based Approach for Specifying Machine Learning-Enabled Systems

In this online repository, we provide all the material involved in our work. This includes participants' characterizations, transcriptions, questionnaires and the final version of the artifacts that comprise PerSpecML. In the following, we outline the material.

Content

Academic Validation

Filename	Description
ACAD_Specification_Assignment.pdf	ML-Enabled System Specification Assignment used in the context of in the of two courses on SE for data science.
ACAD_Catologue_of_Concerns.png	Catalog of concerns used in the academic validation
ACAD_FollowUp-Questionnaire.pdf	Follow-up questionnaire used in the academic validation to get feedback of the participants.

Static Validation

Filename	Description
STATIC_Candidate_Solution.png	Candidate solution for specifying ML-enabled systems.
STATIC_Characterization_Questionnaire.pdf	Characterization questionnaire used in the static validation.
STATIC_Specification_Project_A.png	Retroactively specification for Project A involved in the static validation
STATIC_Specification_Project_B.png	Retroactively specification for Project B involved in the static validation
STATIC_FollowUp_Questionnaire.pdf	Follow-up questionnaire used in the static validation to get feedback of the participants.
STATIC_Transcription.pdf	Transcription of the focus group involved in the static validation.

Dynamic Validation

Filename	Description
DYNAMIC_FollowUp_Questionnaire.pdf	Follow-up questionnaire used in the dynamic validation to get feedback of the participants.
DYNAMIC_Transcription.pdf	Transcription of the two sessions involved in the dynamic validation.
https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPcnYrn0=?share_link_id=304092229021	Specifications for <i>Product Classification</i> Project and <i>Mercado</i> Project using PerSpecML.

Final version of the artifacts

Filename	Description
FINAL Artifacts_PerSpecML.pdf	Final version of the catalog of perspectives and concerns, steps to apply PerSpecML, the perspective-based ML tasks and concern diagram and the corresponding specification template.